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PROJECT WEB-SITE

<http://cure-copernicus.eu/>

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document is describing the CURE (Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe) Project web site. It contains information for the structure of the web site and its contents. The website can be accessed through this link: <http://cure-copernicus.eu/>

1.2 Definitions and acronyms

Acronyms

CURE	Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
EMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service

2 WEB SITE STRUCTURE AND CONTENTS

All CURE web site pages have the same menu bar and footer. The navigation to different pages of the website is achieved from the links in the menu (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The menu of the CURE (Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe) website. The menu is the same in all pages. The CURE logo is on the top left side and the navigation menu on the top right.

The footer contains the links to the Cure Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Researchgate webpages as well as links to the “Terms of us” and “Privacy policy” documents (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The footer of the CURE website. The footer is the same in all pages. The links to social media are on the left and the “Terms of us” and “Privacy policy” documents on the right.

The CURE website includes the following web pages:

2.1 Home

The home page has a registration form for the newsletter (Figure 3). The users can subscribe by putting their email in the corresponding field. By doing so, they will receive updates with the latest news regarding the project.

Figure 3. The CURE website homepage and the “subscribe to newsletter” registration option.

Below the registration is a paragraph outlining the scope of the project along with an image displaying a conceptual illustration of CURE (Figure 4). Within the paragraph there is a link to the DIAS (Data and Information Access Services) website.

Figure 4. Project scope and the Conceptual illustration of CURE development as a cross-cutting structure, based on products derived from four different Copernicus Core Services: CLMS (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service), CAMS (Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service), C3S (Copernicus Climate Change Service) and EMS (Copernicus Emergency Management Service). The CURE system will be built on Copernicus DIAS (Data and Information Access Services) and will contain cross-cutting applications related to urban resilience, reflecting urban sustainability dimensions.

The home page also includes a “Recent News” section that contains the 3 latest posts from the news page and the date they were uploaded. Each post’s title and image links to a relevant page where more information is included (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Recent posts section in Home page. The title and image of the post are also a link to the post’s main page.

2.2 News

News feed of the CURE project. This page will be updated with the latest news regarding the project (Figure 6). Each news post will contain a related image, title, the date and a small summary. The image and the title link to the main page of the post. A “read more” button links to the main page of the post as well.

Figure 5. News page. At the time of this documents it contains one post regarding the Cure kickoff meeting.

The main page of post contains all the information of the news post. There are two “share” buttons, one for sharing the news in facebook and one in twitter. By pressing them, a user can instantly share the post through their social media. Finally, it has a “Recent news” section, similar to the Home page one, for quick navigation to the latest news posts (Figure 6).

Figure 6. The main page of a news post with its title, date, image and related information along with a facebook and twitter share buttons. On the right of the page is a “Recent News” section that links to the 3 latest news posts.

2.3 The Cure System

This page has information on the CURE System and the individual applications. Information regarding the CURE system and the CURE data repository is at the top of the page (Figure 7). Once these are available, there will be link redirecting to the CURE System and the CURE data repository.

Figure 7. The Cure’s system top section page, where the Cure system and the Cure data repository are explained. On the left is an illustration of the Cure prototype.

Following in the page, there is information on the 11 CURE cross-cutting applications. For each application its name, a related image, the developing organizations, the cities of implementations and a description are given (Figure 8). The name of each organization links to their website.

Figure 8. The second section of the CURE System page where the 11 applications are described. On the left each application has a related image. On the right is the name of the application. Below that are the names of the organizations that will develop them, the cities of implementation and information regarding the application. The organization names are also link to their respective websites.

2.4 Publications

The “Publications” in the menu of the website is a dropdown that consists of 3 separate categories (Figure 9):

- **Newsletters**

At the time of this document the project has no newsletter, so this link is empty. In future updates it will link to a page that contains the CURE newsletters.

- **Deliverables**

At the time of this document the project has not published a deliverable so this link is empty. In future updates it will link to a page that contains all the CURE public deliverables.

- **Journals & Conferences**

This link leads to the Journals & Conferences page, which contains all published scientific articles from the CURE project. For each publication, the full citation is displayed and it links to the full document (Figure 10).

- **Published Material**

This link leads to the other publishing material of the CURE project, i.e. articles in the press, newspapers, magazines, project leaflets etc.

Figure 9. The “Publications” dropdown menu. It has 4 links. The first will lead to Newsletters issues (Currently there are no Newsletters). The second will lead to the reports of the project Deliverables (Currently there are no published reports). The third leads to all published papers of the CURE project in journals and conferences. The fourth will lead to all other published material.

Figure 10. The Journals and Conferences page contains all published papers from the project. For each publication are displayed, in this order from top to bottom, its title, the authors, the publisher or conference, the date of publication and the abstract. The title links to the full paper document.

2.5 About

The About page has information for all the partners of the project. For each partner there is a Logo of the organization, their acronym, full name, location, a description of their contribution in project and a dedicated link button for their website (Figure 11). The Logo and acronym are also linking to their website.

Figure 11. The about page of the website. All partners of the project are presented here. On the left of the page is the Logo of each organization. On the right, from top to bottom, is their acronym, full name and location, a summary of their contribution in the CURE project and a button that redirects to their website. The logo and acronym also serve as a similar link.

2.6 Contact

The Contact page on top section has a form from where a user can send a message to the website administrator directly from the website. The form requires the input of a name, an email and a message. All 3 input fields are mandatory. After all fields are filled the message is sent by pressing the “Submit” button (Figure 12).

Figure 12. The contact form in the Contact page. There are 3 mandatory input fields and a “Submit” button. From top to bottom the fields require the name, the email and a message of the sender user. The messages are sent to the website administrator.

The second section of the Contact page contains the address of Remote Sensing Lab (Coordinator) and contact information of its director Dr. Nektarios Chrysoulakis. The contact information includes his email, phone number and Fax (Figure 13).

Dr. Nektarios Chrysoulakis

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Figure 13. The address and contact information of the CURE coordinator in the second section of the Contact page.